

ONLINE LEARNING BENEFITS TO THE STUDENTS IN COVID-19

(A Case Study of Rajamahendravaram city, East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India)

Dr. Annavarapu Lavanya Kumari¹

ABSTRACT

Educational institutes across the world have closed due to the COVID-19 pandemic jeopardizing the academic calendars. Most educational institutes have shifted to online learning platforms to keep the academic activities continue. However, the questions about the preparedness, designing and effectiveness of e-learning is still not clearly understood, particularly for a developing country like India, where the technical constraints like suitability of devices and bandwidth availability poses a serious challenge. In this study, explored the student's preferences for various attributes of online classes, which will be helpful to design effective online learning environment.

The results indicated that majority of the respondents (70 per cent) are ready to opt for online classes to manage the curriculum during this pandemic. Majority of the students preferred to use smart phone for online learning. Using content analysis, it is found that students prefer recorded classes with quiz at the end of each class to improve the effectiveness of learning. The students opined that flexibility and convenience of online classes makes it attractive option, whereas broadband connectivity issues in rural areas makes it a challenge for students to make use of online learning initiatives. However, in higher education system where many courses are practical oriented, shifting completely to online mode may not be possible and need to device a hybrid mode, the insights from this article can be helpful in designing the curriculum for the new model.

Key Words: The COVID-19 Pandemic; Online Education; Online Courses; Higher Education

¹ Dr. Annavarapu Lavanya Kumari, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Economics, College of Arts and Commerce, Adikavi Nannayya University, Rajamahendravaram, East Godavari Dt., Andhra Pradesh, India.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The spread of COVID-19 has led to the closure of educational institutions all over the world. This tested the preparedness of educational institutions and universities to deal with a crisis that requires help of advanced technology including hardware and software to enable effective online learning. Such closure accelerated the development of the online learning environments so that learning would not be disrupted. Many institutions have become interested in how best to deliver course content online, engage learners and conduct assessments. Hence, COVID-19 while being a hazard to humanity has evolved institutions to invest in online learning.

Online learning systems are web-based software for distributing, tracking, and managing courses over the Internet. It involves the implementation of advancements in technology to direct, design and deliver the learning content, and to facilitate two-way communication between students and faculty. They contain features such as whiteboards, chat rooms, polls, quizzes, discussion forums and surveys that allow instructors and students to communicate online and share course content side by side. These can offer productive and convenient ways to achieve learning goals. In Pakistan, the institutions are using Microsoft Teams, Google meet, Edmodo and Moodle as learning management systems along with their applications for video conferencing. Other commonly used video conferencing solutions include Zoom, Skype for business, WebEx and Adobe connect etc.

They reported good technology access, online skills, and preparedness for online discussions among participants across the medical education continuum. With the increase in use of online modalities during COVID-19, it is necessary to assess their effectiveness with regards to teaching and learning from various stakeholders. Therefore, the current study explores the perception of faculty members and students regarding the advantages.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The core objective of this research study is to explore, examine and analyze the benefits, conditions of the students in online education in different educational institutions. In this background, the present study examines the following research objectives specifically:

- To investigate the online education during the COVID 19 period.
- To acquaint with benefits of student in different colleges in Rajamahendravaram.

1.3 Methodology

Methodology makes a study more scientific and realistic objectives. The present study is conducted at Rajamahendravarm City which is situated in, East Godavari district. The data for this study was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected through interview schedules, interviews and observations.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Based on the literature, many studies (Ebner et al., 2020; Mayer, 2020; Wu et al., 2020; Favale et al., 2020; Radha et al., 2020; Hasan and Bao, 2020) discussed e-learning during the coronavirus pandemic, unfortunately, no study tried to know the impression on students who are the focal element in the e-learning. Therefore, it is very significant to know their perspectives of e-learning since they are influenced by this type of learning. This study aims at exploring the overall EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students' perspectives towards the implementation of online learning and exploring challenges and barriers of the online learning that appeared during the COVID-19 pandemic. Hadhrami and Al Saadi (2021), that online learning: makes it possible for learners to take up a course without attending an educational institution; gives learners the benefit of taking up a course from their home or from any place they find comfortable; it also enables learners to get credible certifications and improve their qualifications. Khabbaz and Najjar (2015) investigated students' language learning strategies in a Moodle-based language acquisition program, and the study found that emerging technologies in language learning could hinder autonomous learning due to challenges posed by new technology.

3. THE BENEFITS OF ONLINE EDUCATION TO SELECTED STUDENTS IN RAJAMAHENDRAVARAM

Quality standards have to be determined by comprehensive research in order to constitute functional infrastructure. But there is some uncertainty about the quality for online education in reality. In the literature organizations dealing with online education like NEA, SREB, NACOL, Sloan-C have improved quality standards for online education. There is no obvious information about whether quality standards developed by other countries have been used for online education in Turkey. For that reason, quality standards must be determined for online education to guide how to constitute functional infrastructure at online education foundations. Also, to what extent do students taking online courses give importance to the standards and at

what level higher education institutions giving online courses apply the standards must be identified accurately in Higher Education Institutions serving online course.

This study aimed at exploring the advantages and disadvantages of the online learning system implemented during COVID-19 Pandemic from different educational institutions students in Rajamahendravaram. To achieve the objectives of the study, qualitative approach was used. The sample of the study consisted of 50 students who were chosen purposely from the schools, colleges and the University in Rajamahendravaram. A semi-structured interview was used to collect data and analyse the data.

The study generated the following findings: E-learning saves time, money and effort; it is active in humanities faculties to some extent but it is inactive in science faculties; it encourages students' self-learning and it enables them to listen to recorded lectures many times; it causes social isolation between students; some students resort to cheating in exams; most students face technical problems while using online learning.

Table 1- Distribution of level of education in the Respondents

Sl.No	Education	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
1	Below 10 th	9	11	20	40.00
2	Intermediate	6	4	10	20.00
3	Degree	3	7	10	20.00
4	P. G	4	6	10	20.00
	Total	22	28	50	100

Source: Based on field work

The above Table1 shows that the student sample collected from different educational institutions in the study area i.e., 40 per cent are studying 10th standard. Around 20 per cent of the respondent is studying at Intermediate level and Degree level each. Finally, around 20 per cent are studying Post Graduation.

Table 2- Distribution of Students as Age Group

Sl.No	Age Group	Respondents	Percentage
1	< 16	20	40.00
2	16&17	10	10.00
3	18	10	10.00
4	> 20	10	10.00
	Total	50	100.00

Source: Based on field work

The above Table shows that the students around 40 per cent were in the age group of <16 followed by ten per cent each in age group of 16 & 17 years, 18 years and above 20 years of age.

Table 3- Distribution of level of Benefits in the Respondents

Benefits	Below 10th	Intermediate	Degree	P. G	Total	Percentage
Improving Communication Skills	6	3	5	2	13	26.00
Learning About New Things	5	2	1	1	09	18.00
Easy Way To join classes	4	3	2	2	11	22.00
Convenience and flexibility	3	1	4	4	12	24.00
Others	2	1	1	1	05	10.00
Total	20	10	10	10	50	100.00

Source: Based on field work

The above Table three shows in the study area 26 percent of the respondents are expressed that their improving Communication Skills are increased due to online education. About 24 percent of the respondents are expressed that their Convenience and flexibility through online education the sample 22 percent of the respondents stated that are easy way to join classes. The rest of respondents 18 percent of the respondents are opined that they are learning about new things on through this education.

So, let us have a look at some of the benefits of online learning for school students.

❖ **Convenience**

This is the most important benefit of online learning for school students. Learning and teaching can be done at home with the help of digital devices like smart phones, tablets or laptops. Online learning saves time and enables to focus on other productive activities. It also allows students to choose new topics they want to learn and skip the familiar ones.

Students can study and improve their skills staying at home conveniently. In this case, parents will take care and also, they get enough required personal guidance. They may enjoy freedom to do whatever they want and whenever they like to learn new concepts may use their time

for learning and practicing. They can listen to recorded lecture anytime and complete the task. Since everything is available online, accessing study material and learning new things becomes very convenient.

❖ **Flexibility**

Fixed time tables and fixed time need to be followed in off line school schedule. Whereas online classes help to have flexibility of using time for various subjects according to their wish and interest and balance study matters. If the students are slow learners they can get help from parents and take good time to grasp the concept. Online learning helps students to become more focused and attentive in meeting their targets. They can also take help of their teachers through video calls, chats, communication and interaction for better learning outcomes. With online learning programs, parents can teach their kids anytime and anywhere. It helps students and parents with unlimited access with their school curriculum. Sometimes they need not wait for their teachers to take a lesson. Even parents can tackle that situation at home for better understanding.

❖ **Cost-Effective**

Online learning programs are very affordable. Students can save travelling time and money. It only requires an internet connection and devices like smart phones, laptops, computers or tablets. Parents need to spend more for offline schooling or college studies. Online learning platforms are more economical compared to offline classes. Even after school, they can take an online learning programme to improve knowledge, skills and also in academics with respect to tests, assignments, projects, exams etc. Textbooks also are available at free of cost online.

❖ **Fun and easy**

Nowadays school students are more interested in learning with fun activities. They are able to learn more effectively with online classes which have more interesting features, videos, images, documentaries etc. Due to advanced technology, everyone is aware of the digital world and its applications. Whenever you want to study or refer to any study material, online learning can be more effective.

❖ **Availability of Resources**

Online learning platforms have abundant study materials. Students can watch multiple documentaries, videos, chapters and units for all the subjects of every class. They just need to type the key concept in the search engine. They can extract information on any topic for

learning. Parents can help their children in case of any queries or doubts related to their curriculum. And also, can approach their teachers for any doubts and queries. Both traditional and online learning are good in their own way. Instead of comparing both focuses on getting benefits from available learning sources.

❖ **Personalized Guidance**

It is well known fact that students in schools are always familiar with the use of technology and browsing study materials for learning purposes. Along with that personal guidance is also very important for better learning outcomes. Parents and teachers can help them in identifying their weaknesses and strengths related to their learning. Sometimes they might not get enough attention required in the classroom. But with the help of online learning, this concern seems to be taken care of. Parents are the primary source of personal guidance to their children at home. It is important that parents provide personal attention to their performance during the learning process. Also, student-teacher interaction can help to develop problem-solving skills.

❖ **Availability of Instructor**

The students require a lot of support and guidance during their learning process from teachers and parents. Parents can act as instructors at home by providing guidance when learning online. They can help them in connecting to teachers whenever they need any clarification and discussion. Teachers are always there to help if they are struggling with concepts or theories.

There are multiple ways to communicate with teacher through email, live chat and telephone. They have another opportunity to get feedback or have Q&A sessions with teachers.

❖ **Group Communication**

Online learning is an important platform for discussion and interaction as well. Students can have group discussions with teachers and fellow classmates which enable them to clarify any queries related to the subject. It offers a platform to connect with teachers and friends via emails chat rooms etc. Also, communicate and interact with experts from various regions or countries.

❖ **Accessibility**

To enhance learning experience, accessibility is the most important factor in education. There are a lot of students who shy away from asking questions in the classroom. In such cases,

online learning helps to improve questioning skills. Since everything is online, accessing study materials and submitting tasks is very convenient.

Sometimes it happens when they are not able to take down notes for a particular chapter for learning. With the help of online resources, can access unlimited study materials. Can get help from elders in downloading the study materials and planning their studies. All the lectures and required reading materials are accessible so that they can easily access them from their home. They can review the course materials repeatedly.

❖ **Quick Delivery of Lessons**

There should be immediate accessibility of reading materials for students. There are abundant resources available on online learning platforms. After school, they can have enough time to think and choose the subjects of their choice. It helps them to choose a variety of topics to improve academic performance. Availability of material is just a click away.

❖ **Less Impact on Environment**

Online learning platforms help students to skip going to school at times of an emergency. Then can learn by sitting at home with the complete guidance of parents and teachers. In such cases, there is less use of infrastructure and travel and less impact on the environment. You can save gas and also vehicle maintenance.

❖ **Feedback and Assessment**

Students are able to get feedback on their performance in online programmes. They can identify their mistakes based on feedback. It helps to identify weaknesses and strengths. Parents and teachers can track their progress.

With this platform teachers are able to create tests, quizzes, assignments and projects using pre existing question banks. It also helps to have an automated system for marking their tests and assignments which makes teachers' jobs easy. Online learning provides the most advanced real-time assessment tools for student progress.

❖ **Improves retention quality**

Online learning enhances retention power among students. It explains concepts and theories in the form of videos, images, descriptions, documentaries, charts etc. so that they can remember easily. It makes it easier for students with respect to equations, problem-solving, etc. Its ultimate goal is to retain information for a longer period of time. When students have the right to choose their own content learning becomes easy and effective. With the

experience, they can choose tools that are comfortable and convenient in the learning process.

❖ **Technical Skills**

Online learning is providing a platform for students to learn new tools that can enhance their learning experience. With reporting tools and analytics, they can automate the marking system, and digital tests to track the progress of their performance. There are no geographical barriers for such learning platforms. They find resources from any part of the world.

Learning online skills are very important not just in schools but also in accessing information, communication, interaction, collaboration, etc. It helps to develop new skills in using digital gadgets. For example, creating and sharing documents, and using videos and audio materials for assignments or projects.

❖ **Improves Self Discipline**

Online learning enhances learning abilities not only in academics but also in an overall improvement of individual personality. It enhances self-motivation, responsibility and time management skills along with learning. With this, they learn self-discipline in managing time and tasks. It not only helps in self-discipline but often transmits to other areas of life such as fitness, ethics, lifestyle and relationships with parents, friends, school and society.

Conclusion:

While it is too early to see how COVID-19 will ultimately affect the accelerated adoption of digital learning, it is clear that the wheels of change have been set in motion. It is time to prioritize learning, not put it on the backburner. And it is, perhaps, the one time in history when the corporate Learning and Development narrative will reflect a positive outcome from a negative calamity.

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